

AESTHETIC CLINICAL EVALUATION OF ANRONAL TEETH RESTORATIONS

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Introduction. In the modern world, a beautiful smile is associated with health and self-confidence. In the last 20 years, patients have made more and more demands on the aesthetic component of dental treatment. This article presents a clinical case of the treatment of adentia of both jaws with the manufacture of restorations based on natural teeth. It is indicative how a simple base with a single base color for the manufacture of restorations is formed from an initially complex initial situation.

The high aesthetic requirements for anterior teeth restorations that exist in modern society, as you know, stimulate the constant search, development and optimization of new technologies and restorative materials. However, not only technologies need to be improved, but also approaches to assessing the aesthetic parameters of natural teeth, since the reproduction of these characteristics in restorations is a rather difficult and ambiguous task. It is necessary to recreate the anatomical shape and color, which has many nuances (tone, brightness, saturation), and also take into account all the optical properties of the teeth, which are also diverse - transparency, translucency, opalescence, fluorescence [1,3,7] . To obtain the maximum effect in the course of aesthetic restoration, it is necessary, and this is obvious, an objective assessment of the optical characteristics of both natural teeth and materials used for restoration. The evaluation of the transparency and color of the hard tissues of the teeth to be

restored, as a rule, is carried out visually.

The performed restoration work is evaluated in the same way [1,2,4]. This means that objective and, at the same time, simple and affordable methods for determining these aesthetic parameters have not yet been developed, especially since, as you know, modern photocomposite materials , including universal microhybrid and nanofilled ones , usually already have transparent shades of at least three degrees of transparency [5]. In this regard, it must be stated that the lack of a method for an objective clinical assessment of the transparency of tooth enamel and restorations is one of the urgent problems of restorative dentistry.

Literature analysis and methods. In modern dentistry, the variety of materials and technologies that allow the implementation of individual treatment concepts are welcomed by both patients and members of professional teams.

However, such an aspect as complexity often causes serious problems.

Especially in restorative dentistry, it is often necessary to carry out complex prosthetics of the upper and lower jaws. In this case, you need to get a general idea, analyze the situation and build a treatment plan. A 53-year-old female patient complaining of aesthetics and problems with chewing and soreness.

Poor quality restorations, limited aesthetics. Not restored shortened dentition of the upper and lower jaws.

P		3														
NW	R	k k	p l	O	O		k z						O	kz	Fri	R
HF	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
LF	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
NW		O z	k z	Fri	T o								kz	kz	O	O

P-mobility, SZ-state of the tooth, HF-upper jaw, LF-lower jaw. Teeth condition: K-caries, D-defect, Pl -filling, IR-artificial crown, IZ-artificial tooth, V-inlay, I-implant , KZ-tooth root, O-missing tooth, Pt - periodontitis .k to - root caries , p - Mobility: 1,2,3.

Purpose of treatment. The main goal of the treatment is to restore a functional stable occlusal relationship and harmonious maxillofacial aesthetics.

This requires surgical treatment and, in the area of the 35th tooth, the installation of a pin as an additional support[6].

Surgery. The patient underwent surgical preparation of the oral cavity for prosthetics, which consisted in the removal of the roots of teeth 12,26,35,36 and 46 teeth, as well as traction of the teeth of 17.27 teeth.

Therapeutic training . Treatment of periodontitis of the 45th tooth, restoration of the 44th tooth.

Results. To create identical research conditions in all patients, a number of indices were determined before the restoration of the teeth. The intensity index of tooth decay by caries (KPU) in the first group of patients was 6.66 ± 0.18 , in the second group - 6.27 ± 0.18 . The indicators of structural and functional acid

resistance of tooth enamel according to the enamel resistance test (ER) in patients of both groups were quite close: in the first group - 3.18 ± 0.12 points, in the second group - 3.07 ± 0.10 points. The hygienic index of Fedorov- Volodkina in patients of both groups practically did not differ: in patients of the first group it was 1.12 ± 0.26 points, in the second group - 1.16 ± 0.03 points. The complex periodontal index (CPI) in the first group of patients was 1.15 ± 0.10 points, in the second - 1.12 ± 0.07 points. Thus, all relevant indicators in patients of both groups do not have significant differences between themselves ($p > 0.05$), which indicates identical conditions for the study [7]. EOD data of teeth in patients of both groups did not exceed 2–6 μA (in patients of the first group, the indicators were $4.26 \pm 0.13 \mu\text{A}$, in patients of the second group - $4.07 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{A}$), and this confirms that in all teeth, the restoration of which was carried out during the study, the pulp was viable. A day after the restoration, a visual examination of all restoration work was carried out according to the criteria provided for by the proposed evaluation system. In patients of the first group, 6 works (10.52% of the total) had a discrepancy in transparency, of which 5 works (8.77%) also had a discrepancy between the color of the restorations and the hard tissues of the restored teeth. In patients of the second group, all restorations were rated “acceptable” according to the “transparency match” criterion, while 2 restorations (3.38%) required correction according to the “color match” criterion. According to the criteria "state of the contact point" and "marginal fit of the material to the gingival wall" in accordance with the system proposed by us and according to the USPHS criteria, all restorations of the anterior teeth in patients of both groups were rated with the highest marks. Further evaluation of the performed restoration work was carried out after 6 and 12 months. It should be noted that the indicators of KPU, TER, hygiene index and KPI in these terms in patients of both studied groups changed slightly compared to the initial level, and still did not have a significant difference between themselves ($p > 0.05$)[8]. EOD data of restored teeth were within the normal range. After 6 months, 95 patients were examined with

107 restorations (92.24% of the initial number of restorations), of which 50 restorations were in patients of the first group, 57 in patients of the second group. transparency, it was found that a discrepancy according to this criterion (“unacceptable” rating) in the first group of patients was detected in 8 cases (16.0%), in the second group - in 4 (7.01%). According to the criterion of “color matching”, 5 restorations (10%) in the first group of patients and 4 (7.01%) in the second group received unsatisfactory ratings. All of these restorations were among those that received an “unacceptable” rating and according to the criterion “transparency compliance” .

The final fixation is carried out after the final control of all the main parameters of the restoration using a known technology.

Healthy soft tissues adhere freely to the ceramic surface . The x-ray shows a stable situation. The height of the occlusion, the shape of the incisal edges and the plane of occlusion correspond to the situation. Ceramic restorations complement the natural anterior and mandibular teeth in shape and color and blend harmoniously with the patient's face.

After fixation: functionally and aesthetically successful integration

Discussion. Comprehensive restorative treatment requires a clear concept.

Goals and ways to achieve them must be defined in advance. Thanks to this, the practical steps - even with high complexity - can be carried out relatively simply.

This facilitates treatment for all involved and at the same time allows the highest demands to be met.

The obtained clinical results indicate a rather high efficiency of the objective approaches we proposed to determine the aesthetic parameters of restored anterior teeth using computer analysis of a digital image when planning a future restoration.

The binary evaluation system (“acceptable” or “unacceptable”) makes it possible to reasonably select from the performed restorations works that do not meet high aesthetic criteria.

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